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Research Article

Critical Connections: Unravelling Adverse Drug Reactions and IV Incompatibility in High-Risk Medications

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ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) and Intravenous (IV) incompatibilities are critical concerns in clinical settings as they can affect patient safety and the effectiveness of treatment. This study investigates the frequency and types of ADRs and IV incompatibilities associated with High-Risk Medications (HRMs) in a tertiary care hospital and offers recommendations for preventing these issues. **Methods:** A six-month prospective observational study was conducted across the General Medicine, Cardiology, and Intensive Care Unit departments of a 1000-bed teaching hospital to assess ADRs and IV incompatibilities related to HRMs. **Results:** Out of 97 prescriptions, 27 ADRs were identified, with heparin being the most frequent cause (51.5%), followed by insulin (47.5%) and potassium chloride (45.4%). Heparin-related ADRs primarily included hematuria (50%), decreased hemoglobin (25%), rashes (12.5%), and thrombophlebitis (12.5%). Insulin was associated with five hypoglycemic episodes. Potassium chloride caused vomiting (50%) and thrombophlebitis (50%). Additionally, 230 IV infusion errors were noted, with the most common errors being unrecorded diluent (44%), unrecorded infusion rate (32%), unrecorded concentration (23%), and four cases of IV drug incompatibilities (2%). **Interpretation & Conclusion:** The study underscores the necessity for improved prescribing practices and adherence to guidelines. It also suggests implementing targeted interventions and enhancing pharmacovigilance to improve patient safety and treatment effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare settings are most often faced with the difficult problem of Adverse Drug Reactions

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(ADR) and Intravenous (IV) incompatibilities especially in tertiary care hospitals where complexity of patients' cases and treatments is higher. ADRs are any unintended injurious effect caused by a drug which occurs at normal doses used for prophylaxis, diagnosis or therapy [1]. IV incompatibilities are when two or more substances react adversely upon mixing leading to reduced drug efficacy, precipitation or toxic effects. ADRs and IV incompatibilities occur more frequently with high-risk medications possessing narrow therapeutic indices as well as complex pharmacokinetics [7]. These problems can result in serious harm to patients, longer hospital stays and increased costs for health care providers. To develop strategies that reduce such risks and enhance patient safety it is important to know the frequency of these events, their types, and what they imply about. The drugs analyzed in this study is taken from the ISMP list of high -alert medications in acute care setting [22]. The main objective of this study is to establish the prevalence and types of ADRs and IV incompatibilities found mainly on prescriptions taken from tertiary care teaching hospital [9]. In addition, the study will suggest how ADR's & IV incompatibilities can be prevented and safe practices and handling of high-risk medications that has to be improved.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

The study was conducted at a 1000-bedded multi-specialty hospital located in Coimbatore. The research centered on departments within the hospital exhibiting a high prevalence of High-Alert Medications, specifically targeting the ICU, Cardiology, and General Medicine units. Collaboration was sought from the Pharmacy Practice department and senior physicians to ensure comprehensive coverage and expert input

throughout the study. A prospective observational study design was employed over a duration of six months to gather data and analyze trends related to High-Alert Medications. This approach allowed for real-time observation and documentation of medication administration practices, adverse events, and patient outcomes. The study included a sample size of 97 cases, carefully selected to represent a diverse range of medical conditions, treatment regimens, and patient demographics within the targeted departments.

Data Collection

Data collection for this study was conducted by trained pharmacists, encompassing several key steps. Data on demographics (age, gender), clinical findings (diagnosis, comorbid conditions), and prescription details (drug name, dosage, frequency, route of administration) were collected.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients of 18 years and above age group
- Patients who have been prescribed with one or more High-Alert Medication in their prescription
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Pregnancy and lactating women.
- Patients who did not provide informed consent.
- Incomplete patient records that lacked necessary information for analysis

Statistical Analysis

Data was entered into Microsoft Excel 365 and analyzed. Descriptive statistics, including mean, frequencies, percentages, were used to summarize the findings. The prevalence of ADRs and IV

incompatibilities was calculated, and the most commonly implicated drugs were identified.

with a percentage of 68.05% compared to females 31.96%.

RESULTS:

Gender Based Categorisation:

Table 1: Gender Categorisation (n=97)

Age Based Categorization:

Gender	Number Of Patients	Percentage (%)
Male	66	68.05
Female	31	31.96

The study shows that a higher proportion of males have been prescribed with High-Risk medications

Figure:1 Distribution of High-Risk Medication Prescriptions Based on Age (N=97)

From the study data, the maximum number of study population was in the age group of 60-99 years and the mean age was found to be 68.07. We observed that the prescribing of High-Risk Medications was more in old adults/geriatrics of 55.68% followed by middle-aged adults of 37.12% and young adults of 7.22%.

Intensive Care Unit	49	50.52
Cardiology	31	31.96
General Medicine	17	17.53

Table 2: Distribution Of High-Risk Medications in Various Departments (n=97)

Department	Number Of Prescriptions	Percentage (%)
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In our study the percentage of HRM prescriptions were found predominantly higher in Intensive Care Unit which was 50.52%, since the use of HRM was very high than the other departments, the next most commonly used is in Cardiology department 31.96% followed by General Medicine department 17.53%.

Table:3 Adverse Drug Reactions of High-Risk Medications (n = 27)

S. No.	Drug	Reaction	Frequency	Naranjo's scale score
1.	Potassium chloride	Vomiting	2	4; Possible ADR
		Thrombophlebitis	2	4; Possible ADR

2.	Heparin	Hematuria	4	7; Probable ADR
		Decreased hemoglobin	2	4; Possible ADR
		Rashes	1	4; Possible ADR
		Thrombophlebitis	1	4; Possible ADR
3.	Insulin	Hypoglycemia	5	8; Probable ADR
4.	Enoxaparin	Thrombocytopenia	2	4; Possible ADR
5.	Tramadol	Constipation	1	4; Possible ADR
6.	Atracurium	Hypoxemia	2	3; Possible ADR
7.	Midazolam	Hypoxemia	3	3; Probable ADR
8.	Fentanyl	Respiratory depression	1	5; Possible ADR
9.	Dextrose 25%	Hyperglycemia	1	7; Probable ADR

Table-3, summarizes the adverse drug reactions (ADRs) associated with various medications, evaluated using the Naranjo scale. The statistical analysis includes frequency distributions and classifications based on the Naranjo scale scores. Based on the Naranjo score the most recorded was (Score 4) where 10 ADRs (58.8%) occurred,

following it (Score 3 & 7) - 2 ADRs each (11.8%), (Score 5 & 8)- 1 ADR each (5.9%). The majority of ADRs reported (82.4%) were classified as possible and a smaller proportion (17.6%) of ADRs were classified as probable, which strongly indicates a relationship between the drug and the adverse drug reaction.

Figure 2: Categorisation Of Iv Infusion Errors with High-Risk Medications (N=230)

In our study, we meticulously identified and categorized various types of intravenous (IV) infusion errors directly associated with High-Risk Medications. Figure 2 – Represents a total of 230

errors were found in which diluent not recorded accounts for 43.92% followed by infusion rate not recorded 31.74%, concentration not recorded 22.61% and IV incompatibility 1.74% .

Table 4: High Risk Medication with IV Infusion Errors (N=230)

Drugs	Concentration Not Mentioned	Diluent Not Mentioned	Infusion Rate Not Mentioned
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Tramadol	X	X	X
Dextrose	✓	✓	X
Insulin	X	✓	X
Potassium Chloride	X	✓	✓
Heparin	X	✓	✓
Dobutamine	X	✓	✓
Labetalol	X	✓	✓
Propofol	X	X	✓
Fentanyl	X	✓	X
Midazolam	X	✓	X
Calcium Gluconate	X	✓	✓
Sodium Bicarbonate	X	X	✓
Epinephrine	✓	X	X
Amiodarone	X	✓	✓
Morphine	X	✓	✓
Magnesium Sulphate	X	✓	✓
Atracurium	✓	X	✓
Succinyl Chloine	✓	X	X
Vecuronium	✓	X	X
Atropine	✓	X	X

Table-4, Represents each medication with IV infusion errors represented by a distinct symbol, ✓- Documented in MAR, X- Not documented in MAR. (MAR- Medication Administration Record).

Table 5: IV Incompatibilities of High-Risk Medications

S. No.	Drug 1	Drug 2	Effect/Result	Type Of Incompatibility
1.	Fentanyl (Infusion)	Pantoprazole (Infusion)	Precipitation	Physical
2.	Ceftriaxone Sodium (Infusion)	Calcium Gluconate (Infusion)	Precipitation	Physical
3.	Dobutamine (Infusion)	Pantoprazole (Bolus)	Precipitation	Physical
4.	Ceftriaxone Sodium (Infusion)	Ringer Lactate (Infusion)	Precipitation	Physical

Table 5- represents the IV incompatibilities that occurred during the usage of high risk medications in the included departments. All the incompatibilities were identified and resolved without causing any harm to the patients.

DISCUSSION

The present observational study established the adverse drug reaction profile and causality assessment of High-risk medications with Naranjo scale.^[5] A total of 97 prescriptions were analyzed. The current study reported a majority of people

with use of HRM were ≥ 60 years, similar to the study of Subbiah et al ^[23]. Our study highlights male population were more frequently prescribed with HRM and affected, which was in par with the results of study conducted by Arjun et al, (2012).^[24] This study was conducted in three

major departments selected through a pilot study, which includes cardiology, ICU and general medicine among which ICU accounted for 63% followed by general medicine 19%, and cardiology 18%. Analyzing 97 prescriptions, we could identify 27 ADRs with the use of High-Risk medications in which heparin ranks first with highest number of ADRs (29.7%), followed by insulin (18.5%) and potassium chloride (14.8%). The major reactions observed with the use of heparin was hematuria (50%) which is probable, other reactions such as decreased hemoglobin (25%), rashes (12.5%) and thrombophlebitis (12.5%) falls under possible range calculated using Naranjo scale. All these results coincide with the study conducted by Piazza G. et al.^[9] Insulin was the second most frequently prescribed drug that resulted in ADR, where it caused five episodes of hypoglycemia after administration where all the events were probable, which is similar to the results of Shanthi G.^[20] in which the highest ADR recorded was hypoglycemia. Thereafter, patients receiving potassium chloride suffered from vomiting (50%) and thrombophlebitis (50%) classified under possible range. Most of the errors reported in our study falls under mild to moderate class and some of the errors were not preventable. These findings were also observed in the study conducted by Kassere S et al, where no severe ADR was reported.^[12] This study also evaluated the use of IV infusion of HRM and the associated errors.

Upon analyzing 97 medication charts, 230 errors were identified, which is similar to a study conducted by Marsilio et al., where 100 medication charts were analyzed, revealing 68% IV incompatibilities^[21]. We categorized the IV incompatibilities into diluent unrecorded, followed by infusion rate unrecorded, concentration unrecorded, and IV incompatibility. These findings were compared to a similar study on errors associated with IV infusion in critical care conducted by Summa Sorgini et al.^[17] Definitions of errors were established a priori based on the policies and practices at the study site^[17]. According to the categorization, 'diluent unrecorded' accounted for the highest number of errors, with 101 errors (44%), followed by 'infusion rate unrecorded' with 73 errors (32%), 'concentration unrecorded' with 52 errors (23%), and IV incompatibilities noted in 4 drugs (2%). These IV incompatibilities were analyzed and resolved using the Micromedex Drug Database And Lexi drug as references, both available through the Department of Pharmacy Practice. In our study, 29 (87.8%) probable IV incompatibilities were identified and prevented, while only 4 (12.2%) definite incompatibilities occurred. In a study conducted by Marsilio et al.^[21], midazolam and cefepime were identified as the most common incompatible drug pair. In our study, pantoprazole, commonly prescribed for gastrointestinal disorders, was found to be frequently incompatible with xenobiotics,

followed by analgesics. Additionally, the improper selection of diluent solutions (e.g., Ringer's lactate solution containing calcium chloride) increases the risk of forming calcium crystals when mixed with ceftriaxone. These drug incompatibilities were commonly observed with frequently used medications such as pantoprazole and ceftriaxone. Therefore, teaching sessions should be provided to nurses to raise awareness before administering these drugs. Attention must be paid to preventing such errors, and strategies should be developed to reduce the incidence of errors while handling all medicated solutions.

Recommendations For Improving Prescribing Practices

1. Training and Education: Proper training is keen while training nurses on recognizing ID, eliminating potential drug side effects (ADEs) and specifics of intravenous incompatibility. These sessions will also help in updating the latest guidelines and protocols.

2. Enforce Strict Adherence to STGs: Implementing HOSPITAL-specific standard treatment guidelines (STGs) and ensuring compliance through periodic audits. Policies could be enforced in the form of penalties on non-compliance as well as rewards for adherence to encourage full adoption.

3.E- systems can be used: (e-prescribing): Prescription of drugs based on a system with detecting drug interactions, incompatibility of IV and ADRs while giving orders which will enable the correction to avoid adverse effects as soon as possible.

4.Pharmacovigilance Programs: Developing comprehensive pharmacovigilance programs to track and reduce reporting of ADRs. They work early to get into the detection, reporting and preventing while affecting patient's health.

5.Patient Education: Proper education of patients about the risks of the drugs especially high-risk medications and prompt reporting of adverse events can be beneficial for early detection and management.

CONCLUSION:

High-risk medications are drugs that bear a heightened risk of causing significant patient harm while they are used in error. The consequences of error are more devastating to patients. When any medication can potentially cause harm, a selected group of drugs "High-Risk Medications (HRMs)" carries a higher risk of patient injury. From the results obtained from study revealed that Continued surveillance and documentation of ADRs should be prioritized, and healthcare providers should be vigilant in recognizing potential ADRs during treatment. To minimize the risk of IV incompatibility, Prescription of drugs should be based on a system with detecting drug interactions, incompatibility of IV and ADRs while giving orders which will enable the correction and prevention of errors. These findings provide valuable insights for healthcare providers aiming for improvised medication safety practices in a tertiary care hospital.

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